

Success Story on Fish Production and Consumption at Shimburit Dam: Implication for Livelihood Improvement in Debre-Elias Woreda

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“Now we sustainably harvest and sale fishes throughout the year and supplement our farm income. This contributes significantly to improve the living conditions and health of our family” – Fishing groups

Introduction

Amhara region is blessed with ample water resources and conducive climatic conditions for both agricultural and fish production. However, the per capita fish consumption, which is not more than 0.5 kg/person/ year, is trivial. Specifically, the experience and habit of fish production and consumption remained unfamiliar in East Gojjam, except for some areas situated near to rivers. Given with rich freshwater, conducive agro-climatic conditions and potential for culture fishery, it is always a puzzle when fish consumption becomes unknown to such areas. In Debre-Elias district, which is the belt of wheat production, a large dam (Shimburit) has been constructed by AGP project. The dam is laid on 48 hectares of land with ultimate purpose of irrigation use. Surprisingly, the idea of fish production that increases the productivity of the dam without any extra costs was not considered from the inception to the completion of the dam. Thus, the dam was completed without any mesh wire, which controls the escapement of fishes through the spillway. In the area, the success of fish production is hindered by lots of factors, such as knowledge and skill gap from production to consumption, fish market, poor extension delivery and non-existence of fishing inputs. This success story highlights how BFALRC¹ bring a breakthrough in the areas where fish production and consumption were unfamiliar.

Interventions by BFALRC

In 2016, one study was conducted to assess the performance of culture fishery and its challenges in Amhara region. The study showed that most of the fishponds are small in size and have not provided adequate benefits due to stunted fish growth and overpopulation. Based on the

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identified problems and its recommendations, BFALRC has realized the vitality of giving more attention to large-sized fishponds and man-made reservoirs/dams. Based on this, BFALRC exert its concentration and effort into the Shimburit dam by providing technical and logistic support for the responsible actors. The key secrets for the success of the intervention are summarized below.

1. Firstly, BFALRC has made exhaustive discussion with livestock and fisheries resource development office of the district. The issues of discussion were: ways of introducing aquaculture in the area, enhancement of water bodies with fish, integration of irrigational schemes with fish production, etc.
2. Provide suggestions on ways of spillway modification so as to prevent fishes that skip through the spillway. Following this, the outlet of the dam has been fenced by mesh wire.
3. After the overall assessment of the dam i.e., water quality, outlet, suitability for fish production and status of the catchment area, the dam was stocked by more than 30,000 fish fingerlings (*O. niloticus*, catfish and common carp).
4. Continuous awareness creation for the district and Kebele level fishery experts to fill the aforementioned skill gaps.

5. Continuous monitoring of the fish growth and water quality status of the dam
6. Forage grass species that serve as livestock feed, breeding ground and at the same time reduce erosion and siltation were planted.

7. After the stocked fishes reached to marketable size, consecutive trainings on ways of fishing, consumption, post-harvest handling, and marketing were provided for farmers, experts and the two fishing groups.

8. Workshop and field days that invited different stakeholders (from regional to local experts and potential fishers) were also held at the site.
9. As an initial capital, BFARLC provided some basic fishing inputs, such as reed boat, gill nets, and trays for fisher groups.
10. In collaboration with the district and local experts, two fishing groups (each has 19 members) has been established.
11. To alleviate the market problem, market linkage has been made with a wholesaler who receives the catch at the landing site

Outputs of the Intervention

BFALRC has successfully promoted fish production and consumption to the local community and the fish experts as well. In addition, two fishing groups have been established from the two bordering Kebeles of the dam and regularly practiced fishing. Thus, the intervention has created an alternative employment opportunity for about 38 (26 male and 12 female) youths. In terms of return, fishers from each group generated more than 70,000 ETB per annum (2020/21). More interestingly, the intervention has brought a behavioral and habit change on the local communities who were not previously consuming fish. Presently, they have understood the nutritional role of fish consumption and start eating fish food. After the practical training and awareness creation on the fish post-harvest handling, fish dish preparation and consumption, three fish restaurant has been opened in the district (Debre Elias). This success also motivate some farmers to participate in fish farming at their backyards for both home consumption (“fish from farmstead to the plate”) and marketing. For instance, two huge fish ponds are constructed at the lower catchment of the dam after the intervention. Another important outcome after the intervention is that Debre-Elias district and its neighboring districts have now giving strong attention to the expansion of aquaculture.

Implications and Handover for Future Expansion

In this intervention, the big lesson is that stunted child growth and malnutrition, which are the worst manifestations of the region, can be reduced by producing and consuming fishes from different man-made dams and reservoirs. It also sheds light that there is a possibility to alleviate the severe unemployment problem by integrating such types of irrigation dams with zero cost fish production system. Thus, the intervention can serve as a springboard for further expansion of culture fisheries at different areas of the region. For the sustainability of such viable enterprise, market linkage should be established to avoid monopolized price setting problem. It also requires a long-term commitment of different stakeholders with adequate infrastructure and financial support to fulfill the fishers’ demand for basic inputs, such as refrigerator, additional gill nets, motorized boat, post-harvest handling and transportation etc.